

The exclusive ion activation arsenal of the Omnitrap platform illustrated

Applications in top down and bottom up proteomics

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The Omnitrap™ platform – Past & Present

Linear Ion Trap
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Omnitrap platform
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The Omnitrap™ platform – Design aspects & Activation network

Electron Source

Plasma Ion Source

EDD
23TAG z=9-

VUV Light Source

Hamamatsu D₂ lamp

The Omnitrap Platform: a Versatile Segmented Linear Ion Trap for Multidimensional Multiple-Stage Tandem MS

Electron Capture Dissociation

Electron Induced Dissociation

Hydrogen Ion Activated Dissociation

Vacuum Ultraviolet Photodissociation

Electron Induced Dissociation of ubiquitin $[M+8H]^{8+}$

35 eV electrons, $\sim 1 \mu\text{A}$ current
IT= 500 ms, 2.5×10^6 charges

New Applications based on the Omnitrap platform

Top Down (MSn)

Antibody sequencing

Bottom-up (ExD)

Peptide sequencing

Bottom-up (IR/UV)

Speed / PTMs

Glycans (EID)

Structural characterization

SS bond dissociation (VUV)

Protein structure & sequencing

Oligonucleotides (EDD)

Lipids (EID)

Identification & structural characterization

Radical Ions (EmI – MS3)

Radical migration network / fundamental studies

MS4 Analysis of Intact mAbs in the Omnitrap platform coupled to a QE Plus

Intact non-reduced denatured mAb

Light Chain
LC & HC Variable Regions
Sequence info between SS links

Charge-reduced LC ions
Sequence info between SS links

Sequence info across
entire Light Chain

MS

slow heating CID

MS2

ECD

MS3

Slow heating CID

MS4

Two-step CID process involving collisional re-activation of high m/z complementary fragments by broadband excitation. Dissociation of the intermolecular bond connecting the light and heavy chains produces a heterogeneous population of fragment ions with variations on the cysteine side chain.

Electron capture leads to charge reduced intact light chain ions and low intensity primary fragments with cleavage positions external to the SS linked regions. Electron capture initiates homolytic cleavage of the SS bonds.

Collisional activation of charge reduced ions produces sequence information throughout the light chain. Spectral complexity due to the heterogeneity of the intermolecular SS bond cleavage is further enhanced by the heterogeneity of the intramolecular SS bond cleavage.

MS4 Experimental Workflow in the Omnitrap QE platform

MS2 Slow-heating CID of Herceptin® 49+ & Broadband-excitation CID of high-mass fragment ions

Slow-heating CID produces a remarkably non-congested spectrum that allows to further select fragment ions for MSn interrogation. ECD or UVPD appear less favorable as a starting step for MSn workflows.

SS bond dissociation has been reported in ECD and UVPD but not under typical sh-CID conditions, as observed here. Additional experiments with the NIST mAb have confirmed the SS bond dissociation by sh-CID.

The broadband excitation frequency range is chosen to induce fragmentation of all heavy ions, which are not isotopically resolved. These high-mass first-generation CID fragments are complementary to the isotopically resolved lower m/z ions. Second-generation be-CID product ions enhance the intensity of the first-generation sh-CID fragments by a factor of 2x – no new fragments are generated in be-CID of high mass ions.

Resolving DC isolation of Light Chain z=11+ in Accumulation Mode

Population enrichment is performed with a single precursor ion and not with an entire population of fragments to avoid losses during ion transfer between trapping regions at both extremes of the available m/z range. The enriched population must also remain near or below the space charge limit of the trap for the same reason.

NL:
1.24E7
TIC MS
20201102_her
c 49+ _ CID
q01 +BBexc
_ ResDC
LC11+ HR

Accumulation OFF
NL ~ 2.9×10^4

Accumulation ON
NL ~ 2.5×10^5

Resolving DC settings:

$f_{RF} = 355.3\text{KHz}$
 $V_{DC} = 53.3\text{V}$
 $t = 6\text{ms}$

isolation window
selected for ion
enrichment

The isolation window contains three main precursor ions produced by dissociation of the intermolecular disulfide bond linking the two chains at three consecutive positions.

Three consecutive cleavages across the intermolecular SS bond linking the heavy and light chains together are identified with high mass accuracy ($\leq \pm 5\text{ppm}$).

ECD of Enriched Light Chain

Gas phase reactions performed in the omnitrap platform involve a two-step CID process producing intact light chain ions in high abundance. The population of the light chain is enriched prior to reactions with low energy electrons. The ECD step produces a series of charge-reduced light chain ions and low abundance ECD fragments.

Charge-reduced light chain ions are transferred back to Q2 and isolated by the application of a resolving DC signal. The isolated charge-reduced light chain ions are subjected to MS4 CID.

ECD settings:

Electron energy ~2eV
Irradiation time 100ms

Slow-heating CID of charge-reduced Light Chain ions

D I Q M T Q S P S S L S A S V G D R V T I T C R A S Q D V N T A V A W Y Q Q K P G K A P K L L I Y S
 A S F L Y S G V P S R F S G S R S G T D F I L T I S S L Q P E D F A T Y Y C Q Q H Y T T P P T F G Q
 G T K V E I K R T V A A P S V F I F P P S D E Q L K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V
 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L S S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K V Y A C E V T H Q G
 L S S P V T K S F N R G E C

a
 b
 c
 z

a : 29%

b : 37%

c : 53%

x : 10%

y : 26%

z : 24%

Sequence coverage : 73.7%

Data processing is performed in PeakFinder

D I Q M T Q S P S S L S A S V G D R V T I T C R A S Q D V N T A V A W Y Q Q K P G K A P K L L I Y S
 A S F L Y S G V P S R F S G S R S G T D F T L T I S S L Q P E D F A T Y Y C Q Q H Y T T P P T F G Q
 G T K V E I K R T V A A P S V F I F P P S D E Q L K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V
 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L S S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K V Y A C E V T H Q G
 L S S P V T K S F N R G E C

a
 x
 b
 y
 c
 z

a : 28% x : 14%
 b : 30% y : 23%
 c : 40% z : 29%

Sequence coverage : 70.9%

Data processing is performed in PeakFinder

Combined sequence information obtained from MS4 CID of LC¹⁰⁺ and MS4 CID of LC⁹⁺

a : 40.8% x : 20.2%
b : 45.1% y : 33.8%
c : 61.5% z : 38.5%

CDR regions

Sequence coverage : 83.1%

a
 x
 b
 y
 c
 z

a : 9% x : 11%
 b : 12% y : 12%
 c : 29% z : 19%

Sequence coverage : 52%

Dynamic range of ion concentration in MS4 ion accumulation mode

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